

THE IMPACT OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT ON ECOLOGICAL SUSTAINABILITY: FOUNDATIONS OF SUSTAINABLE ECOTOURISM

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada empirik tadqiqotlar asosida turizmni rivojlantirish va ekologik barqarorlik o‘rtasidagi munosabatlarni o‘rganib chiqildi. Hukumat qo‘llab-quvvatlashi va siyosat aralashuvi yordamida biznes va atrof-muhit manfaatlari o‘rtasidagi muvozanatni ta‘minlash orqali turizm rivojlanishining ekologik barqarorligini ta‘minlash mumkinligi ushbu maqolada asoslandi.

Kalit so‘zlar: turizmning rivojlanishi va o‘sishi, ekologik barqarorlik va degradatsiya, tabiiy muhit, ekotizim va bioxilma-xillik, ekoturizm.

Аннотация. В данной статье на основе эмпирических исследований рассматривается взаимосвязь между развитием туризма и устойчивостью окружающей среды. В статье утверждается, что экологическая устойчивость развития туризма может быть достигнута путем достижения баланса между интересами бизнеса и окружающей среды посредством государственной поддержки и политического вмешательства.

Ключевые слова: развитие и рост туризма, экологическая устойчивость и деградация, природная среда, экосистема и биоразнообразие, экотуризм.

Abstract. Empirical research has examined the relationship between tourism development and environmental sustainability to propose a framework for sustainable ecotourism. With the help of government support and policy intervention, the environmental sustainability of tourism development can be promoted by striking a balance between business and environmental interests. This article analyzes the above issues

Keywords: tourism development and growth, environmental sustainability and degradation, natural environment, ecosystem and biodiversity, ecotourism framework. The study population includes tourism stakeholders, including tourists, local community representatives, members of the civil administration, hotels and tour operators serving the areas.

Introduction. A total of 650 questionnaires were distributed to respondents, along with a brief description of the main research variables to develop a better understanding. After checking the reliability and validity of the instrument, data analysis was conducted through hierarchical regression. The results of the study showed that a large proportion of the population perceives socio-economic benefits, including employment and business creation, infrastructure development and growth from tourism development.

However, the state of natural and ecological capital has been found to be gradually deteriorating. Along with the social environment, social vulnerability is noted due to overuse of land, the intrusion of foreign cultures, and air and water pollution due to the accumulation of traffic congestion, solid waste, sewage, and carbon emissions.

The study proposed a model framework for sustainable ecotourism development, including the importance of supporting public policy measures to ensure effective conservation

of the environment and natural resources without compromising the economic viability and social well-being of local populations. Furthermore, the variables and constructs studied can be replicated in other areas to seek valuable information for sustainable targeted management in other locations.

Tourism is a vibrant force that encourages travel to explore nature, adventure, wonders and societies, discover cultures, meet people, communicate values and experience new traditions and events. Tourism development attracts tourists to a particular destination to develop and support the tourism industry. Furthermore, environmental sustainability is a future-oriented conscious effort to preserve socio-cultural heritage and conserve natural resources to protect ecological ecosystems while supporting human health and economic well-being.

Environmental sustainability can be reflected in clean and green natural landscapes, thriving biodiversity, sea beaches, desert steppes, socio-cultural values and archaeological heritage, which reflect the motivation of tourists and the readiness of local communities to welcome visitors. In this context, tourism growth and environmental sustainability are interrelated constructs; therefore, tourism development and the growth of tourist arrivals directly affect the quality of sustainable and green tourism.

According to the World Tourism Organization (WTO), tourism is one of the fastest growing industries, contributing more than 10% to global GDP. The number of international tourists increased from twenty-five million in 1950 to 166 million in 1970, reaching 1.442 billion in 2022 and is projected to reach 1.8 billion by 2030. Mobilizing such a large mass of tourists can reduce environmental pollution and its positive impact on employment.

Local pollution in tourist destinations can include air pollution, noise, waste, garbage, sewage, oil and chemicals, architectural and visual pollution, heating, car use, etc. In addition, uncontrolled, excessive and poorly planned tourists have a serious negative impact on environmental quality. This leads to overconsumption of natural resources, deterioration of service quality, and exponential growth in waste and pollution. Furthermore, tourism overcapacity is not a blessing but a problem, such as leaving soil erosion, loss of natural resources, accumulation of waste and air pollution, endangering biodiversity, fragmentation of socio-cultural habitats, and land and sea pollution.

Tourism growth and environmental pollution are being observed in various regions around the world. Countries such as ASEAN are experiencing economic tourism and pollution due to air pollution, climate change and global warming. More than fifty-eight tourist destinations in China are proposing urgent policy measures to mitigate air pollution and improve environmental sustainability.

Similarly, Singapore, the most visited country, faces a negative environmental footprint, calling for a trade-off between tourism development and environmental sustainability. Previous studies have shown that international tourism and tourism-related growth contribute to climate change through increased tourist arrivals, energy consumption, carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, and air pollution. South Asian countries, specifically Sri Lanka and Pakistan, are on the cusp of tourism growth and environmental pollution compared to other countries.

Tourism expansion has been defined as a very harmful environmental cost compared to the socio-economic benefits it provides to host communities. The process of tourism development and its various dynamics revolve around tourism planned for a specific destination or area, which can be defined as ecotourism, sustainable tourism, green tourism or regenerative tourism, etc. The concept of ecotourism is based on a set of well-defined principles such as “environmental protection and education, cultural preservation and experiential and economic

benefits". Ecotourism reduces the impact of tourism on the tourist resources of a particular destination, including physical, social, interactive and psychosomatic impacts.

Ecotourism is also a positive and significant commitment by tourists and hosts to the protection and conservation of all components of the ecological ecosystem. Ecotourism reflects a goal-oriented mindset that is responsible for creating and delivering value to the destination with a high level of concern for local environmental, political, or social issues. Ecotourism is typically distinguished from mass tourism by:

- a. Focusing on low environmental impact.
- b. Sensitivity to and positive impact on local cultures, values, and biodiversity.
- c. Supporting efforts to conserve local resources.
- d. Sharing and delivering the benefits of tourism to local communities.
- e. Local participation in decision-making processes as tourism stakeholders.
- f. Educate tourists and local residents about environmental sensitivity and care, as poorly regulated tourism can threaten ecosystems and local cultures and lead to serious environmental degradation.

Conclusion

Sustainability aims to recognize all impacts of tourism, minimize negative impacts, and maximize positive impacts. Sustainable tourism involves sustainable practices to support the ecology of the destination and its surrounding tourism environment. Sustainable tourism is a natural resource-based tourism that is similar to ecotourism and focuses on creating travel destinations with minimal impact and encourages the exploration of valuable resources for low-impact, conservation, and local community well-being. Ecotourism, on the other hand, encourages tourists to explore and care for the environment, and to participate effectively in nature conservation and cultural activities. Thus, ecotourism encompasses sustainable tourism, while sustainable tourism focuses on the following commitments:

- a. To care for, protect and conserve the environment, natural capital, biodiversity and wildlife.
- b. To ensure the socio-economic well-being of the people living in and around the places visited by tourists.
- c. To identify, rehabilitate, preserve and promote cultural and historical heritage to enhance the visitor experience.
- d. To bring together tourists and local groups for common interests.
- e. To create a wide range of opportunities for tourists.

The maintenance and promotion of a clean environment is essential for the existence of people and biodiversity, for the conduct of business and for the creation of wealth, for the stimulation of growth and development. Through the protection, conservation and appropriate management of the environment, it can be sustainable by reducing toxic pollution, eliminating waste and wastewater, conserving endangered species and protecting the land

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